

Speculation on the Photon Momentum and Electric Field

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We have argued in previous notes that special relativity is often developed from the point of view of a particle with rest mass, leading to the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + c^2 \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)). Then, as a second step, one may obtain the equation $E = c|\mathbf{p}|$ by setting $m_0=0$. This appears to be a straightforward math step to obtain a photon relevant result, but we have suggested in (1) that m_0 represents an inherent force, called inertia (Newton). Thus, special relativity for a particle with rest mass is really linked to this inherent force. In fact, we have suggested in (1), that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ is obtained by finding an equation linear in a particle's inherent force (rest mass) which is linked to E and \mathbf{p} from special relativity and geometry. This, we suggest, is why Dirac linearized ((1)) to find spin $\frac{1}{2}$. The reason for linearization is to have an equation linear in the inherent force, because force appears in $\mathbf{F} = d\mathbf{p}/dt$ in a linear fashion. The rest mass case seems to be largely based on m_0 , inertia, which we call the inherent force. We further argued in previous notes that free particle quantum probability arises from $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x} =$ Lorentz invariant ((2)) because x, t and $x + \hbar \mathbf{p}/p, t + \hbar/E$ give the same result and we consider $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x}$ to act somewhat like a free particle potential.

This suggests that a photon should also have a probability $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$, which is verified as both a photon and particle with rest mass, with the same \mathbf{p} , give rise to the same 2-slit interference. The problem in the photon case is that $m_0=0$ and so no inherent force appears in special relativity. We argue that physically, there must be an inherent force as interactions (as in the 2-slit case) depend on it. In (1) we argued that the inherent force of a photon is the electric field, but this does not appear in ((1)) or ((2)), but emerges from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations. This is why the photon has spin 1 and not spin $\frac{1}{2}$ even though it has the probability $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$. (See (1) for details on the specific equation which gives rise to spin 1.)

Here, we argue that for a particle with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ (i.e. rest mass), $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$, which is a probability which conserves energy and momentum, the momentum and energy are proportional to rest mass (inertia or inherent force) and so $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ is really a probability distribution for inherent force (augmented to E, \mathbf{p} due to the Lorentz boost). In the case of the photon, one still has $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$, but the force is due to the electric field. This begs the question: What is the spatial distribution of the electric field? Is it free to be any function? We argue that given that $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ is the energy/momentum conserving probability from special relativity, the inherent force cannot contradict this distribution. The electric field, which is a real valued function, must be $\cos(-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$. We note that one may formally obtain a classical wave equation from Maxwell's EM equations to find E proportional to $\cos(-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$, but this does not explain the complex probability $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ which holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass. Our objective is to argue that given $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ for a photon, the electric field must behave as $\cos(-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$. Interestingly, the photon momentum density $1/c^2$ Electric field \times Magnetic field is proportional to $\cos(-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \times \cos(-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$. This does not follow $\text{Real}(\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x}))$, but it is the electric field and not momentum in the photon case which is linked to force. We argue that ultimately it is force which governs interactions, even though momentum (not momentum density) is conserved.

Special Relativity and Particle with Rest Mass

A key Lorentz invariant is:

$$-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1))$$

((1)) applies to a particle with rest mass, which we suggest really represents the inherent force of the particle (as stated by Newton who called it inertia). ((1)) is not simply about viewing properties from different frames, in the case of a rest mass particle, it is about viewing an inherent force as seen in different frames. In other words, given that E and p are both proportional to m_0 (rest mass), they are directly linked to the inherent force.

We point out the above because one obtains an equation for a photon from ((1)) by setting $m_0=0$. We argue that this is not simply the removal of a property of a particle, but the removal of the inherent force which controls physical interactions. The photon equation $E=pc$ is obtained by removing the sense of force. This, we argue, is a major issue. We note that in Newtonian mechanics, $F=dp/dt$ for a particle with rest mass. Experiments show that a photon with momentum p creates an impulse when striking a target and given that a photon has E,p , these should be conserved, just as in the particle with rest mass case. An impulse, however, cannot be created without a force. Momentum is not a force of nature. In the particle with rest mass case, it is associated with inertia, which in turn is associated with fundamental forces, but in the case of the photon, one simply has E and p from special relativity, with no notion of force.

Conservation of Energy and Momentum

Conservation of energy and momentum are cornerstones of Newtonian mechanics. In Newtonian mechanics, only elastic collisions conserve particle energy, but overall energy is conserved. Special relativity, which treats (pc,E) as a 4-vector, deals with two conserved quantities in both the particle with rest mass and photon cases. In the above section, we noted that special relativity does not display an inherent force for a photon, but if all one is interested in is the two conserved quantities E,p , then special relativity provides relationships for these. We suggest that this is an important point due to the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((2))$$

((2)) which happens to be both the relativistic and nonrelativistic action for a free particle has the same value for:

$$x,t \text{ and } x+h\bar{p}/p, t+h\bar{E}/E \quad ((3))$$

We have suggested in previous notes that ((3)) leads to a complex probability which essentially enforces conservation of energy and momentum, but creates uncertainty regions in x linked to a fixed p and in t , linked to a fixed E . The probability is:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((4))$$

One may see that $\exp(-iE_1 t + i p_1 x) \exp(-iE_2 t + i p_2 x) = \exp(-iE_3 t + i p_3 x) \exp(-iE_4 t + i p_4 x)$ if

$$E_1 + E_2 = E_3 + E_4 \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \quad ((5))$$

For a particle with rest mass, p is proportional to m_0 , which is like a force called inertia, even though this inertia is linked to fundamental forces. For a particle with rest mass, one may think of momentum directly as a force. For a photon, there is no rest mass and so it is hard to think of momentum as a force, but conservation of momentum for a photon striking a target made of particles with rest mass, shows that the photon momentum is linked with force, but not through m_0 . One might argue that ((4)) does not explicitly show an inherent force as it applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass. Nevertheless, it is used to calculate 2-slit interference results and physical forces must be involved in such an interaction.

One might ask: If inherent forces are so important, why are they absent from ((4))? We argue that ((4)) is not the full quantum free particle picture. In particular, there also exists spin and in (1) we suggest that spin must be linked to inherent force. Thus, ((4)) is sufficient for conservation of E, p effects, but we will argue later that it too is linked to inherent force.

To see how spin arises (1) argues that one must find an equation linear in the inherent force and linked to E, p and geometry. For a particle with rest mass, m_0 is the inherent force and so one only needs to linearize ((1)) as Dirac did. A photon does not have rest mass and so must have a different intrinsic force, namely its electric field (1) and so one needs an equation linear in this field. Maxwell's electromagnetic equations provide such an equation as one may linearize:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5\epsilon_0 \text{ Electric field dot Electric} + .5/\mu_0 \text{ Magnetic B dot B}) + \text{grad dot } 1/\mu_0 \text{ Electric} \times \text{B}] = 0 \quad ((6))$$

We have linearized ((6)) in another note and the spin matrix which emerges is e_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol from the cross product, leading to spin 1. At first one might argue that there is no link with ((4)), but that it is not true. ((6)) follows from Maxwell's em equations, and at the same time Maxwell's equations lead to a classical wave-equation for both Electric field and B , i.e.

$$\text{Electric field is proportional to } \cos(-Et + px) \quad \text{and} \quad B \text{ to } \cos(-Et + px) \quad ((7))$$

In principle, Maxwell's equations only give $\cos(-wt + kx)$, but w must be proportional to E and, k to p to have Lorentz invariance.

One may see that unlike the particle with rest mass case, photon momentum density is not proportional to the inherent force (electric field), but rather to:

$$\cos(-Et + px) \cos(-Et + px) \quad ((8))$$

Momentum density, however, is not the driver of interactions, but rather the inherent force.

We ask: How is it that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ applies to a photon and $\cos(-Et+px)$ to the inherent force, the electric field. Is it a coincidence that $\cos(-Et+px)$ is the real part of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$?

Argument For Photon Inherent Force (electric field) Behaving as $\cos(-Et+px)$

We have argued above that based on conservation of energy and momentum and special relativity ($-Et+px$ Lorentz invariant), there exists a probability ((4)). This probability predicts 2-slit interference which necessarily involves a physical interaction with the walls of the slits (as this is a probabilistic calculation). For a particle with rest mass, the force is with $mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, through whatever fundamental force exists. $\exp(ipx)$ is a spatial profile of the p momentum hit which is also an inherent force hit. If this is the case, we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ should also represent the inherent force in the photon case, because the photon interferes in the same manner as a particle with rest mass and an interaction must involve an inherent force. We suggest that given $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and the acceptance of the electric field as the photon's inherent force means that the electric field should be proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$ (as it is a real valued field), even without Maxwell's electromagnetic equations. Maxwell's equations for the inherent force are linked with the quantum free particle wavefunction (without spin) of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, we argue.

Conclusion

The main conclusion of this note is that special relativity deals with p,E (which form a 4-vector), but are also conserved quantities for elastic collisions. In the case of a rest mass, we argue that the rest mass is the inherent force of the particle which is directly associated with interactions even though a fundamental force is required as well. For a particle with rest mass, E and p are proportional to this rest mass. From $\exp(ipx)$ from $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, the complex probability which conserves E,p , one may see p (proportional to m_0) as the inherent force and $\exp(ipx)$ as its spatial probability.

A photon on the other hand has $m_0=0$ and so the usual E,p equations of special relativity do not reveal any inherent force. One, however, must exist and furthermore, it must have a spatial profile associated with $\exp(ipx)$ because the photon undergoes the same 2-slit interference as a particle with rest mass, and this requires an interaction with an inherent force. For the photon, momentum density goes as $\cos(-Et+px)*\cos(-Et+px)$, but there is no contraction with $\exp(ipx)$ as one wishes to consider the probability of the inherent force which is the electric field. Thus, it is the probability density of the electric field and not of momentum which governs 2-slit interference. That being said, the electric field must behave as $\cos(-Et+px)$ which includes E,p . The fact that Maxwell's EM equations confirm this, suggests that they anticipate quantum mechanics as well as special relativity (as we argue that two are intertwined).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Quantum Spin, Intrinsic Force and Special Relativity Part 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2026)